

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IMPORTANCE IN THE FORMATION OF METACOGNITIVE ACTIVITY

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Annotation: this article contains information on how to supplement the solution of several current attitudes in the teaching of school physics in today's educational system with new pedagogical technologies. Also presented are analyzes of increasing the level of their use of ICT and the formation of metacognitive activity in the process of training young pedagogical teachers.

Keywords: motivation, differential education, interactive education, personalized teaching, innovative methods, reflection.

Today in the educational system there are a number of current attitudes in the teaching of school physics. Filling these attitudes with new pedagogical Technologies is the task of young pedagogical teachers. It is advisable to dwell separately on several attitudes in the teaching of school physics below.

1. Student motivation: physics is often perceived as a complex and difficult-to-understand science. It is necessary to interest students in physics and increase their motivation.

2. Practical training: it is important to put theoretical knowledge into practice. It is necessary to show students the practical importance of physics by conducting experiments, laboratory work and giving real-life examples.

3. The role of technology: modern technologies, such as simulation programs or interactive educational platforms, can be used in teaching physics. However, in order to effectively apply these technologies, it is necessary to improve the skills of teachers.

4. Advanced learning methods: it is important to use differential learning methods, that is, to teach according to the individual needs of each student.

5. Integrating physics with other disciplines: teaching physics and mathematics together, as well as integrating it with other disciplines such as chemistry or biology, can help students generate a deeper understanding.

6. Strengthening the link between theoretical and practical knowledge: it is possible to improve the understanding of students by linking theoretical knowledge with practical examples.

7. Teacher qualifications: professional development of teachers and their introduction to new pedagogical methods is necessary.

To solve these problems, it is necessary to introduce innovations in the educational system, train teachers and use modern pedagogical techniques. Also, in the process of training teachers, of course, it is advisable to increase the level of their use of ICT. The reason is, today it is difficult to imagine an educational system without information technologies. The use of Information Technology in shooting helps to make the educational process more efficient and interesting. Below we will analyze some of the advantages of Information Technology in the teaching process:

1. Interactive education: with the help of Information Technology, students have the opportunity to work with interactive materials. This increases their interest and makes classes more lively.

2. Resource access: through the Internet, access to various resources, articles, videos and e-books becomes easier. This allows students to gain wider knowledge.

3. Distance Education: Information Technology provides distance learning opportunities that allow access to education regardless of geographic limitations.

4. Personalized teaching: teachers can use information technology to create personalized programs to suit the needs of each student.

5. Self-assessment: through various online tests and programs, students can independently assess their knowledge.

6. Collaboration and communication: various platforms (e.g. forums, social networks) can be used to promote communication between teacher and students.

7. Innovative methods: teachers can modernize classes using information technology so that they can try new pedagogical techniques.

8. Data analysis: new ideas can be developed to analyze and improve the educational process based on information collected using information technology.

For the effective use of information technology, it is important that teachers participate in the appropriate trainings and get acquainted with new tools. This not only increases the quality of education, but also increases the motivation of students.

Information technology also plays an important role in shaping metacognitive activity. Metacognitive activity involves the awareness of self-control and learning processes. And information technology allows you to make

these processes more efficient and convenient. Below are some aspects of the role of Information Technology in the formation of metacognitive activity:

1. Self-assessment: with information technology, students can use a variety of tools to assess their knowledge. For example, through online tests or interactive platforms, there is an opportunity to determine their level of knowledge.

2. Teaching and learning process management: through information technology, the educational process becomes more interactive and flexible. Teachers can use a variety of resources to develop students' self-control skills.

3. Resource access: through the Internet, students have easy access to many different resources, which helps them expand knowledge and test new strategies.

4. Cooperation: with the help of Information Technology, students have the opportunity to exchange ideas with each other, collaborate in solving problems, which serves to develop their metacognitive skills.

5. Reflection: teachers can use information technology to encourage students to reflect on activities that are being conducted in the teaching process. This increases their thinking skills.

6. Personalized education: it is possible to create personalized educational programs using information technology to help each student develop their metacognitive abilities to suit their needs.

In general, the role of Information Technology in the formation of metacognitive activity is enormous, and there is a need to further expand the use of these tools in modern educational systems. It will be possible to create new modern pedagogical technologies of teaching using these technologies.

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